

Washback effects in language programs: A sociocultural perspective

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This study explores how university entrance exam washback impacts language teaching and learning programs at a madrasa in Indonesia's sociocultural context. Data were collected via semi-structured interviews, phone calls, voice notes, and WhatsApp with the headmaster, an English coordinator, two English teachers, a sociology teacher, and two student parents. Content analysis revealed how washback has changed the school's language programs. The findings showed that the madrasa's teaching practices differ from typical schools in curriculum design, policies, methods, materials, and activities. Its curriculum prioritizes state university entrance tests, splitting the national curriculum into three semesters for standard subjects and three for test preparation. Teachers rely on international textbooks and online resources instead of government materials. Their methods focus on memorization, repetition, and drills, rather than communicative language instruction. Assessments measure student proficiency rather than improving teaching. This approach enables students to excel in university entrance exams and succeed at global universities.

Keywords: Indonesian Boarding Schools; Islamic Boarding School; Language Assessment; Language Program; Washback

1. Introduction

In a 'post-colonial world' that has changed into a small village due to intercommunication, international trade, tourism, information technology, and so forth, lingua francas are inevitable—be they 'local' (e.g., Persian, à la Salmani Nodoushan (2024)) or 'international' (e.g., English à la Koné (2024)). Native speakers of English are no longer 'points of departure' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023), English as an international language (EIL) is being taught all over the world, and world Englishes have overridden the traditional American and British standard varieties of English.

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Under this circumstance, high-stakes language tests (e.g., the *TOEFL*, the *IELTS*, etc.) are used as selection tools for a wide variety of purposes. Wherever a high-stakes test is used, ‘coaching’—i.e., training for test performance—is preferred to ‘teaching’—educating for achievement; test performance is likely prioritized at the cost of language proficiency. In a situation like this, ‘washback’ is inevitable. This article investigates the effects of ‘washback’ in language programs at Madrasa, an Islamic boarding school, in Indonesia. Although washback has been analyzed extensively in the Indonesian context, most studies have focused on public schools at varied levels and national examinations (Saukah, 2015; Sundayana et al., 2018). The Islamic boarding school where this research was conducted is known for its graduates continuing to receive tertiary education at reputable Indonesian and foreign universities. Nevertheless, the Ministry of Education has proposed a new policy related to university entrance exams (Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, 2022). The change includes a scholastic test for university entrance, assessing the student’s academic potential, mathematics reasoning, English literacy, and Indonesian literacy, and removing other subjects (Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, 2022). Thus, this change draws attention to what policy is stipulated in the school to allow it to adjust to the new governmental policy and how the teaching and learning process is conducted at the school to accommodate the changes in the policy.

2. Background

Washback can be defined as (a) teaching to the test (Salmani Nodoushan, 2021), (b) the tendency of students or teachers to tailor their teaching and learning to meet the demands of the test when the test is essential for their future life (Buck, 1988), (c) the effect of testing on teaching and learning (Hughes, 1989), (d) the idea that testing affects teaching (Alderson & Wall, 1993; Wall & Alderson, 1993), or (e) the use of standardized tests to foster language learning. Messick (1996, p. 241) defined washback as “. . . the extent to which the introduction and use of a test influence language teachers and learners to do things they would not otherwise do that promote or inhibit language learning.” Furthermore, Bailey (1996) reported that washback is important but under-researched.

High-stakes testing that most likely influences teachers, students, and other education stakeholders is washback-prone testing, which, according to Stobart and Eggen (2012), has severe consequences for one stakeholder. Some examples of high-stakes tests include the *TOEFL* and the *IELTS*, which are used to determine whether test-takers can be admitted to universities in the United States or the United Kingdom. The Malaysian University English Test (MUET) in Malaysia (Mahmud et al., 2021) and the National Selection for the Admission

of New University Students (*Seleksi Bersama Masuk Perguruan Tinggi Negeri*, or SBMPTN, and *Seleksi Nasional Berbasis Tes*, or SNBT) in Indonesia are high-stakes tests.

Washback effects are observable or mediated. In the case of observable washback, learners “do things they would not necessarily otherwise do” (Alderson & Wall, 1993, p. 117) without the test, such as showing enthusiasm in test-related preparation and practices, superficial learning, preference for tested materials, and private tutoring, while teachers narrow down the curriculum, engaging in test-oriented teaching and practices (Tsang & Isaacs, 2022), serving after-school classes, scheduling test practices, and relying more on drills and repetitions. Mediated washback, according to Tsang and Isaacs (2022), refers to the influences of tests on mediating factors underlying learners’ observable actions, whether at intrinsic or extrinsic levels, such as the type, amount, and intensity of washback.

Washback can be intended or unintended. Intended washback refers to the actions, reactions, or situations intended by the test developers (Khan et al., 2019), while unintended washback refers to the effects the test developers intend to mitigate (Cheng et al., 2015). Intended washback is often referred to as positive, whereas unintended washback is negative. Tests are frequently intended to drive change and guide curriculum (Cheng et al., 2004) and measurement-directed instruction (Hawkey, 2006). The tested constructs can be considered important teaching content for teachers, students, and curriculum developers. This may lead teachers to change the curriculum content, the materials taught, and the methods used, or direct students to adjust their learning. Unintended, negative washback may include narrowing down the curriculum (Hamp-Lyons, 2000), teachers’ ignorance of learning materials that do not directly contribute to passing the exams (Vernon, 1956), students’ anxiety, after-school classes, cram schools, teachers’ teaching to the test, reliance on drills and rote learning, or hangover effects, which according to Whitehead (2014), refer to the continuation of test effects long after they are administered. In addition to positive and negative effects, washback, according to Hawkey (2006), can be neutral. One test in one context may exert positive or negative effects, whereas, in another context, it might not have any effect.

2.1. How does washback work?

To understand how washback works, washback effect models and hypotheses are usually discussed. Hughes (1993) distinguished between participants, processes, and products. Participants whose perceptions and attitudes can be influenced by the tests include teachers, students, administrators, curriculum developers, headmasters, and materials developers. According to Hughes (1993), processes are any actions participants take that may contribute to

teaching and learning (p. 2), such as teaching strategies, worksheets, learning time extensions, and test drills. Products, according to Hughes (1993), are what students learn (facts, skills) and the quality of learning (fluency). In this model, according to Hughes (1993, p. 2), a test may first affect the participants' perceptions and attitudes toward their teaching and learning tasks, which later will influence what the teachers do, what the students learn, and how they learn inside and outside classrooms, which later will affect learning outcomes.

Based on the model proposed by Hughes (1993) and Alderson and Wall's (1993) hypotheses, Bailey (1996) conceptualized a model to understand washback. In the model, the test influences participants involved in various processes that produce products specific to teachers or learners. Not only does the test affect the participants, but they can also provide feedback on the test, a phenomenon called wash forward by Van Lier (1988, as cited in Bailey, 1996). According to Bailey (1996), information about a test received by the test-takers and its influence is called washback to the learners. Information about a student's test results obtained by teachers, administrators, curriculum developers, and counselors is called washback for the programs (Bailey, 1996). In Hughes' (1993) model, Wall and Alderson's (1993) hypotheses, and Bailey's (1996) model, the coverage of participants is quite comprehensive, including students, teachers, administrators, curriculum developers, and test and materials developers.

Promoting beneficial/positive washback is the main objective of test developers (Bailey, 1996), and Messick (1996) suggested that there should be a narrow gap between what learners do when learning a language and what they do when preparing for a test to optimize positive washback. Brown (1997) summarized the strategies for promoting positive washback into five categories: (a) test design, (b) test content, (c) logistics, (d) interpretation, and (e) analysis factors. Test designs that promote positive washback promote criterion-referenced tests, objective achievement tests, or direct testing. Brown (1997), citing various resources, argued that test contents that use more open-ended items and assess higher-order thinking are more likely to produce positive washback because logistical factors can lead to positive washback. Brown (1997) also suggested that positive washback could, among others, be promoted when examination results are credible, believable, and fair to test takers, when predictive validity studies of public examinations are conducted, and when examination boards have research capacity.

2.2. Sociocultural perspective

John-Steiner and Mahn (1996) argued that the sociocultural theory of learning and development was first developed by Vygotsky in Russia in the 1920s and 1930s, proposing that human activities occur in social contexts mediated by

semiotic systems that can be best discerned in historical contexts (p. 92). Vygotsky (1962) believes that every function of the cultural development of a child occurs twice in two aspects first in the relation between people as an inter-psychological category, and then within the child as an intra-psychological category (Valsiner, 1987, cited in John-Steiner & Mahn, 1996). As John-Steiner and Mahn (1996) quoted, semiotic mediation is vital to all aspects of Vygotsky's scholarship. Semiotic mechanisms mediate social and individual functioning and connect the internal and external, as well as the social and individual.

In sociocultural theory, teachers are not the only party that contributes to learning outcomes. At the same time, students are active agents that contribute to the learning outcome, but not passive objects of learning. Breen (2001, cited in Booth, 2012) theorizes that, to understand how students learn another language, we have to examine not only the learning outcomes of learners but also the learning processes and students' contributions to those process; students' attributes and their environment also need to be taken into account (Breen, 2001, cited in Booth, 2012). Students' contributions differ from context to context, so their actions are contextually situated. Wider communities, including what happened to students in the past, now, and in the future, according to Breen (2012, in Booth, 2018), will shape students' contributions to learning processes and learning outcomes. Activity theory, developed from Vygotsky's ideas, posits that human behavior results from the integration of socially, culturally, and historically constructed forms of mediation into human activity (Lantolf, 2000, cited in Booth, 2012).

In terms of the madrasa context, Indonesia has a solid sociocultural resilience. Studies on the sociocultural dimensions of boarding schools have found that Islamic values are strongly upheld by the students in the boarding schools and are considered necessary; other cultures do not influence religious values (Munawaroh et al., 2022; Saefudin et al., 2021). However, some Islamic boarding schools require students to use English because they are prepared to engage in further studies and science (Taib et al., 2021).

Taylor (2015) asserted that social constructivist theory relies on the importance of negotiation and consensus when making sense collectively of personal experiences. In this sense, the learning environment will be more discursive in which students negotiate their developing canonical understandings. The elements that are most distinctive in distinguishing sociocultural theories from individual cognitive approaches, according to Esmonde (2016), include the following:

- (1) Cultural artifacts (both tools and signs) mediate human activity; this means that artifacts form an inextricable part of human cognition (rather than bearing some causal relationship with cognition);
- (2) learning should be studied as it occurs in everyday life, not just in the laboratory;
- (3) as people cross boundaries between different contexts, their learning endures and shifts; therefore, the unit of analysis for the study of learning goes beyond the individual and must include aspects of context; and
- (4) multiple historical timescales are relevant for the study of learning.

2.3. Washback studies from a sociocultural perspective

Washback studies rooted in sociocultural perspectives are rare. Booth (2012, 2018) applied sociocultural theory to examine the effects of the washback of the *TOEIC* on students' learning by studying participants, processes, and products, as proposed in Bailey's model (1996). The attributes studied included students' needs, motives, and goals. Tsang and Issacs (2022), supporting Booth (2012), argued that there is a need to treat washback on learning not as an independent but a socially situated phenomenon under which learners' observable actions are driven by an array of mediating factors, not only within but also beyond the individual level. Tsang and Issacs (2022) studied the washback effects identified by learners, learners' self-reported intrinsic and extrinsic factors mediating washback, and the paths of influence between the types of washback effects and the categories of mediating factors. Furthermore, the strongest predictors varied for each type of washback effect, yet they were all significantly affected by at least one intrinsic and one extrinsic factor. Hence, washback on the learning construct is driven by an array of intertwining and potentially competing forces (Tsang & Isaacs, 2022).

Concerning the application of the sociocultural perspective in washback studies, Barnes (2017, p. 1) stated that "... the very definition of washback is problematic due to its reliance on what constitutes 'good' teaching and learning practices, which can differ from one educational context to another." Thus, positive or negative washback are dependent on context (Barnes, 2017), while the true nature of test washback can be understood only by taking into account the educational, cultural, political, and social contexts in which the test operates (Dawadi, 2021). He reported that several factors, including economic factors, social prestige associated with test performance, parents' educational background, and perceived importance of English, affected the nature of the washback of a high-stakes test.

Studies interrogating washback from the perspective of participants, processes, and products should consider the situations where the phenomenon

occurs. Holm and Kousholt (2019, p. 918) believed that “testing affects the understanding and construction of pupils’ cleverness—something that occurs both as part of test practice (formal construction of cleverness) and as part of more complex everyday life (informal construction of cleverness).” In this line of argument, Razavipour et al. (2020, p. 1058), studying the role of motivation in washback, asserted that “given the complexity of test preparation and washback, theories of motivation must be complemented by broader social considerations to explain test preparation and test washback.” Other works do not explicitly state that they are underpinned by sociocultural theory as a framework.

Along the same lines, the present study examines teachers’ and schools’ self-reported responses to university selection tests and their responses to test changes at an Islamic boarding school in Indonesia.

3. Method

To meet the research objective, a qualitative approach with a case study design was selected. Yin (2003) argued that case studies can be used to investigate social phenomena in natural settings (cf. Patten, 2000, 2001). The design is appropriate because the issue was observed in a natural setting without intervention.

3.1. Research site and participants

The research was conducted to depict the washback effect from a sociocultural perspective at the International Standard Madrasa in East Java, Indonesia. The rationale for selecting this research site was that most graduates from the school were admitted to reputable higher education institutions in Indonesia and abroad (Middle East, Europe, and America), and many students from the school participated in, and won, various national and international competitions. Many considered these reasons to be achievements for a school that was established in 2006. The research team interviewed the participants several times. The participants were selected purposely to explain the phenomena; The participants included the headmaster, an English subject coordinator, two English teachers, a sociology teacher, and two student parents. The headmaster and English subject coordinator were interviewed to examine changes in the level of school policy after the government changed the national examination policy. Second, language and sociology teachers were asked to share their teaching practices before and after the changes made by the government and their perceptions and attitudes toward these changes. Finally, the rationale for involving the students’ parents was to explain the washback from participants who did not engage in the teaching and learning process.

3.2. Instruments

In this study, interviews were the primary instrument used to gather information and collect data from the participants. The research team also used phone calls, voice notes, written WhatsApp messages, and online interviews to obtain additional information from the participants. The interviews were conducted in Bahasa Indonesia.

3.3. Procedure

The interviews were conducted after obtaining consent from the headmaster for data collection. The researchers and the headmaster identified the participants who were suitable and willing to participate in the study, and the interviews were conducted. After the interviews were completed, the data analysis was conducted following Creswell and Creswell's (2018) stages of qualitative data analysis: (a) organizing and preparing data for the analysis, (b) reading and inspecting the data, (c) coding the data, (d) generating descriptions of the data, and (e) interpreting the descriptions of the data.

The interview results were arranged according to the date and the interview order, and all the interview results in audio or video formats were transcribed. After transcribing the interviews, data related to washback from the sociocultural perspective were highlighted. Following this stage, selected data were translated into English, and descriptions of the data were generated according to school responses to cope with the changes in the state university selection test and responses to university entrance test results. Besides conducting multiple interviews to maintain the reliability and validity of the data, the interview results were also sent to the participants to ensure that what they stated in the interviews was reported correctly in the article.

4. Results

After obtaining consent from the stakeholders, an interview process was initiated. Based on the interviews with different stakeholders, it seemed that the coping mechanism of the school for the changes in the university admission test was by (a) adjusting the curriculum, (b) creating policies to support students' preparation, (c) selecting appropriate teaching and learning materials, and (d) refining students' schedules. The interviews also revealed the response of the school to future changes in the university admission test.

4.1. School responses in coping with the state university selection test

After interviewing a student's guardians about their perspectives on the state university selection test and the school system's aspirations, the washback met the parents' and students' goals. For example, the parents of a student we

interviewed stated that they hoped their son would pursue an IT career while maintaining and following their religious values. They believed that boarding schools would provide their son with a well-rounded (balanced) education in both areas. The father stated:

Excerpt 1: We hope that he can achieve his goal of becoming an IT expert, but he still holds religious values. In the beginning, boarding school was my son's choice. Then, we sought information about the school's performance, which is famous for balancing academic and religious knowledge and values . . . we decided to choose a boarding school that would be able to help my son achieve his goal in life. (A student's parent)

As seen in Excerpt 1, the parent's rationale for selecting the school was affected by the objectives set by the parents and prospective students. By understanding parents' and students' goals, the school can align its policies with those objectives. This alignment was evident when the school's founders saw themselves as educators who could cater to different public needs. Therefore, the boarding school they established with an adjusted curriculum was directed at strengthening students' Islamic studies and academic achievements. One indicator of a solid academic school is its graduates being able to attend their dream universities.

The school has tailored its approach by making adjustments and decision to meet the parents' and students' aspirations and expectations. These changes in aspects of schooling complied with the students' and parents' aspirations to create a balanced separation between academic and religious fields. The school's effort to sustain accomplishment and fulfill these expectations was evident when the school's leaders decided on several actions that helped satisfy demands.

4.2. Curriculum

The changes in the curriculum driven by the state university selection test were displayed when the school decided to condense the curriculum by combining and completing the national secondary school curriculum in only three out of six semesters as can be seen in Excerpts 2 and 3.

Excerpt 2: Year 10 and Year 11 students completed the non-university selection test content in three semesters. The equivalent of six semesters is reduced to 1.5 years. During the first three semesters, students focus on preparing for a non-computer-based university entrance test. In Year 12, computer-based learning materials are provided for students based on their chosen study plan. Students in

social and humanities departments, such as Indonesian, English, sociology, economy, geography, and history, and those in natural science and technology departments, like Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and Biology, are provided with relevant materials. (Headmaster)

Excerpt 3: Year 1 students should be grouped according to their intended university. Students planning to attend universities in the Middle East are grouped. In Year 3, there are 11 classes on computer-based test preparation. Some students plan to attend vocational schools organized by ministries other than the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology, the Ministry of Religious Affairs, and one foreign country class, such as those attending universities in Singapore, the USA, or Turkey. (English teacher)

Completing the national secondary school curriculum in three semesters, semesters 1, 2, and 3, and semesters 4 to 6, are used for university selection test preparation as elaborated in Excerpt 2. This condensation of the curriculum action has to be implemented because all schools in Indonesia should follow the national curriculum, whether under the Ministry of National Education, Culture, Research, and Technology (MoE) or the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MoRA), for their students to be able to join SNBP (a kind of university entrance selection). Since students' academic grades from semesters 1 to 5 are still used as the basis for university entrance, the academic records should cover semesters 1 to 5.

In Excerpt 3, in addition to re-packing the curriculum to be more condensed, study adjustments and adaptations to the targeted universities' requirements based on students' plans in the curriculum were also conducted. For example, if students plan to attend Australian or UK universities, the courses will include the *IELTS* and academic writing. However, if students plan to be admitted to American universities, the *TOEFL*, academic writing, and the *SAT* are included in the curriculum. Different inclusions in the curriculum are made when the students intend to register for the *TOEFL* and *Qur'an* memorization at Arabic-speaking universities. Therefore, the curriculum is adjusted to the test required by each university, plus subject content mastery. These adjustments differ from standard practice in the Indonesian school system, where students are prepared for different university entrance tests, and this practice is conducted for years in the school to satisfy the needs of parents and students.

In addition to concentrating on the curriculum, the school has designed a university-like curriculum. In regular secondary schools, subject matters are assigned by the government, and all subjects taught at schools are usually taught by one teacher. However, in research site boarding schools, each subject

has more than one teacher, for example, two teachers teaching sociology. In contrast, four teachers taught English: a writing teacher, a speaking teacher, a reading teacher, and a listening teacher. In addition, students will have different instructors for language preparation at the language center, especially for the *IELTS*, the *TOEFL*, and other language tests required by the universities they attend.

4.3. School policy

In the interviews, the headmaster and the English teacher also reported that the school had developed two policies: academic potential tests, and student groupings based on targeted universities. These policies ensure that students select suitable and appropriate study programs and universities. Excerpts 4 and 5 show the school policies from the interviews with the headmaster and an English teacher.

Excerpt 4: To ensure academic progress, we administer scholastic tests during the early stages of students' studies. Newly admitted students must attend matriculation classes in their first semester. Decisions regarding continued education are made in Year 11, and more specific identification in Year 12. (Headmaster)

Excerpt 5: Year one students need to be grouped according to their intended university. In year two, Middle East-bound students are placed in a single group. Year three offers 11 computer-based test preparation classes. Some students plan to attend vocational schools run by ministries other than the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology and the Ministry of Religious Affairs. Additionally, there is a foreign country class for those traveling to countries such as Singapore, the USA, and Turkey. (English Teacher)

The school provides activities tailored to each grade level based on interview results. In the first semester, all newly admitted students must take matriculation classes to improve their knowledge and understanding. The school recognizes students from diverse academic backgrounds and provides equal opportunities. In year 11, students take a standardized test similar to the *SAT* to measure their academic potential, learning style, and interests. This test ensures that students have the necessary skills to succeed in their tertiary education. Year 12 will be followed up with a more detailed assessment of student's academic abilities and skills.

Excerpt 5 presents a more specific action from the school to help students achieve what they aspire to accomplish by grouping the students based on

their needs. Starting in year 11, the school groups the students based on the universities they are enrolled in. At the moment, there are four groups of students in semesters 4 to 6, namely:

- (1) State University Entrance Test organized by state universities.
- (2) Overseas Islamic Studies groups, such as those visiting Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Morocco, and Sudan.
- (3) International Overseas groups like those in Malaysia, the United States of America, European countries, Japan, South Korea, China, Singapore, etc.
- (4) Attend military or police academies, accountant schools, tax schools, government bureaucrats, etc.

The grouping makes the class more homogenous, makes the treatment more accessible, and efficiently meets students' needs.

4.4. Teaching practices and learning material selection

Washback affects not only the curriculum and school policies but also the learning material selection and teaching practices. As shown in Excerpt 6, the English teacher elaborated on the selection of learning materials used at the school and some enrichment materials to increase students' understanding and proficiency.

Excerpt 6: For English, we download, see, and adapt the books to become the students' books, forming a compilation. The books do not reference the Cambridge curriculum, but the publishers, yes...like Cambridge Press, Longman Press, or Pearson. The titles were varied. We selected international resources that university students typically use. The reason we use overseas books as references is because we expect that the outcome is that students will obtain an English proficiency certificate and then take university entrance tests. For those requirements in English literacy, we refer to them to make them relevant. In addition to teaching, we have to learn. We subscribe to digital and online resources. (English Teacher)

Excerpt 6 revealed that learning material selection was based on students' future needs. Teachers prefer to orient learning materials to university entrance tests rather than senior secondary English schools' curricula. The current English secondary curriculum is underpinned by Systemic and Functional Linguistics (SFL) and a genre-based curriculum. However, for example, the interviewed English teacher should have considered genre-based

teaching and learning, especially for Year 3 because the English Literacy test does not cover the entire range of genres covered in the previous semesters. Teachers do not refer to a national curriculum, but they create a test-guided curriculum based on the needs of every university entrance test. Nevertheless, the teachers realized that they should ensure that their students' academic levels are higher than the national curriculum. Teachers design materials relevant to the content tested at a level of difficulty similar to those learned and tested at universities.

In addition to increasing learning materials to university-like materials, enrichments are provided for students. IT companies that provide enrichment materials for students, like Ruang Guru (Coursera-like), by inviting the best tutors to come to the school, are also involved. Teachers and students attend seminars and workshops on how to pass university entrance exams. Famous figures from universities and related government institutions are invited to schools to motivate students and teachers. The teachers realize that they should be watchful of changes in university selection tests and adapt quickly to them.

4.5. Students' learning schedules

Excerpt 7 features an interview with the teacher coordinator of an Islamic boarding school where students have a routine of early mornings and late nights.

Excerpt 7: Students will receive academic instruction from 8:30 a.m. to 12:00 p.m., followed by lunch, and then they will continue their studies from 1:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m. From 3:30 p.m. to 5:30 p.m., they will receive instruction in Islamic studies. Afterward, they will have independent study time until 10:00 p.m., when the study time ends, and they can rest and sleep. Early in the morning, at 3:00 a.m., students will wake up to pray and attend a lecture given by the school's founder until 6:00 a.m. They will then take a short break until 8:30 a.m. Students will stay in boarding schools, and their parents will visit on Sundays. The school will take care of meals and laundry, allowing students to focus solely on their studies. (English Coordinator)

Excerpt 7 indicates how the school focuses on students only on learning and developing their performance and how hectic and strict the students' schedule is. The activities of the students displayed in the interview align with the objectives of the students and the parents, which is to balance academic life and religious values. This practice supports what Taib et al. (2021) reported in their study.

4.6. Responses to changes in university entrance test results

During the follow-up interviews, it was revealed that the school has implemented various strategies to adapt to the changes in the university entrance test. The school consistently trains its teaching staff and administration to anticipate regulatory changes. Excerpt 8 provides insight from interviews with the headmaster, teacher coordinator, and sociology teacher.

Excerpt 8: The teachers are already familiar with the academic tests. Last year, the education minister launched a policy of using only the scholastic test in the university entrance test, excluding physics, chemistry, biology, sociology, geography, and economics. We have to design something new to anticipate it. (Headmaster)

Excerpt 9: We will do our best to adapt to the latest university entrance test policies. For SNBP or achievement, we base it on records from year 10. So, in Year 10, we already have grades and scores. We call them try-out grades. Although it is also a two- or three-assessment assessment, we carefully pay attention to students' academic achievement records until their last year. Then, we accumulate all of them in year 12 plus portfolios. Although the students' grades are good, if the portfolios are not linear with the study programs the students plan to take at universities, the school will not support the students' decisions. The school negotiates and advises the students to take more relevant study programs or take the Test-Based National Selection (SNBT). (English Teacher Coordinator)

It is evident from Excerpts 8 and 9 that the school continuously anticipates changes to the university entrance test. Teachers believe that adaptation is key to the success of their students, continuing to their favorite universities, and ensuring that good students come to schools. As seen in Excerpts 8 and 9, the school monitors students' portfolios and discusses study programs and university selections with the students. In addition, recommendations and suggestions are provided to students. Moreover, familiarity with the test is not only intended for students but also for teachers. This policy is applicable when the government alters university entrance exams.

The above findings highlight how an Indonesian boarding school adjusts its curriculum, teaching methods, policies, and extracurricular activities to accommodate the state university selection test while tailoring its students' and parents' academic and religious aspirations. By compressing the national curriculum into three semesters and dedicating the remaining time to preparing for university entrance exams, which include both general and

specialized content, the school aims to cater to the diverse academic ambitions of its students. Whether students aspire to attend domestic or international universities or seek a combination of secular and religious education, schools' strategic approach allows for a personalized educational experience. This approach prioritizes preparing students for university entrance exams while focusing on Islamic studies. Moreover, the school's proactive adaptation to changes in university entrance tests demonstrates its commitment to ensuring that students are well-prepared for higher education. This commitment is reinforced through a rigorous schedule that promotes academic excellence and religious values.

5. Discussion

The research revealed that the reason for the washback was the objectives of the parents and students. These objectives include (1) passing university entrance exams nationally and internationally and (2) balancing academic and religious values. Excerpt 1 demonstrates that the parent of a student enrolled in the school believed that the school could help them achieve these objectives. Additionally, Hughes' (1993) washback classification was used to analyze the effect of the university entrance test on participants, processes, and products. It is possible that positive and negative washback occurred in the school (Bailey, 1996; Cheng et al., 2004; Khan et al., 2019), but this study did not assess the strength of the washback. Although, socioculturally, Islamic values are still the primary concern of parents and teachers, the Madrasa complements these values with students' future foreign language needs.

The research findings on curriculum condensation partly affirm Tsang and Isaacs' (2022) statement and Whitehead's (2014) concern regarding the continuation of test effects. Tsang and Isaacs (2022) stated that washback can make teachers narrow the curriculum down, but the difference between the current research context and that of Tsang and Isaacs (2022) is that the teacher does not narrow the curriculum down but condenses it from six semesters to three semesters; it is the school's decision and seems to be agreed upon and supported by other school stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and students. Whitehead's (2014) continuation of test effects can be seen in the students' informal after-school classes and their heavy reliance on rote learning and drilling methods. Nonetheless, it presumably indicates that the concern from Vernon (1956), Brown (1997), and Hamp-Lyons (2000) about negative or unintended washback and teachers' ignorance of learning materials does not fully occur in the research context. According to Hughes (1993), what happens in the research context is a participant and process washback. The school and teachers follow the national secondary curriculum. Additionally, they focus on the tests students must pass to obtain university admission during the teaching and learning process.

In addition to curriculum change, washback influences how schools establish their policies to help meet the goals of parents and students. University entrance being a high-stakes test for stakeholders (Stobart & Eggen, 2012), the school, for example, determines some uncommon practices in Indonesian secondary schools, like administering scholastic tests. Although scholastic tests in various forms are often administered to secondary school students, especially senior high school students, the scholastic test at the research site is taken as the basis for identifying which university a student can enroll in. Another exciting thing is the student additional grouping system. In Indonesian high schools, students are typically grouped into science, social science, and language concentrations. However, at the research site mentioned in Excerpt 5, students are grouped based on similarities in university requirements, resulting in homogenous classes with similar activities.

The next aspect influenced by the university entrance tests is the selection of teaching practices and learning materials. Due to its reliance on context, good teaching practice is difficult to define (Barnes, 2017; Cheng, 2008). Thus, determining whether the teaching practice at a school is positive or negative washback is challenging. However, to satisfy stakeholders' demands, teaching practices at schools can be seen as successful. The school tries to make students' initial knowledge equal in the matriculation classes. As defined by Buck (1988, see also Alderson & Wall, 1993), these efforts are the adjustment of the teaching and learning process attributed to tests, in this case, university entrance tests. One important note about the influence of tests on the teaching and learning process is that school leaders, teacher coordinators, and teachers still teach and follow the national secondary curriculum, at least in the first three semesters. Changes in teaching and learning processes also create different learning needs in learning materials. In this context, international resources should be included in the second three semesters after students are admitted to school, especially for test-driven activities. This practice strengthens Tsang and Isaacs' (2022) statement regarding preferences for tested materials. Again, this strategy reflects how washback occurs in teaching and learning.

The university entrance exams also make students study harder. Whitehead (2014) noted that as one of the test effects, in this context, students add their own independent study time to some degree until the school decides that they need to make time limitations for students to learn. Students' actions can be categorized as a washback that affects the process, to be exact, learning time extension (Hughes, 1993). This might happen because the students set their bar high and understand what it takes to achieve it. In addition to this, the students need to build their portfolios as required by the school to be admitted to their favorite universities, and these portfolios are checked by the school so that it can monitor each student's progress and development during their high

school study. However, the researchers did not consider students' knowledge gained through independent studies and the contents of their portfolios. The constant anticipation from the school reveals how high the level and prestige of university entrance tests are (Brown, 1997). Furthermore, students and their parents expect schools to frequently adjust to keep up with government policies and international standards. A school's reputation is heavily influenced by where its graduates pursue education.

It is also important to note that this study has at least three limitations. First, the context of this study is a boarding school where students and most teaching staff live in a school complex. Thus, the supervision process from the school to its students' activities and individual learning seems easier to conduct, and schedules can be controlled. This condition is not applicable in most public schools where students and teachers spend only a certain amount of time at school. Second, the system stipulated in the schools that become the research sites in the study does not reflect the status quo of language teaching in Indonesian schools. Although there has been a national regulation in relation to the curriculum, teaching and learning practices, and tests, each school is allowed to create its own policy to tackle the regulation. The school-based policy will enable them to creatively tailor student preparation for the tests. Third, the policy of having more than one teacher for each subject is not feasible in most schools in Indonesia. Schools, in general, have only one teacher for one subject, and curriculum condensation seems impossible.

6. Conclusion

This article provides a sociocultural perspective on the washback effects of university entrance exams at a madrasa in Indonesia. The school's main objective is to ensure that its students pass university entrance tests, excel in their academic education, and uphold Islamic values. This objective results from the aspirations of middle to upper-class Muslim parents and the school's role in meeting public needs.

Interviews with various school stakeholders, including students, parents, headmasters, teacher coordinators, and teachers, revealed that the school takes a different approach to achieving its goals than regular public or private secondary schools. The system implemented at the boarding school in the study context has provided detailed descriptions of how the school tries to accommodate the needs of students and parents. However, one limitation of this study is that the practices depicted in this study seem to be difficult for other institutions to replicate, such as their ability to provide various international textbooks for students.

Differences in teaching and learning practices can include curriculum, school policies, teaching methods, learning materials, and student activities.

Headmasters, English teacher coordinators, and English teachers design curricula guided by state university entrance tests during the teaching and learning process. Teachers adapt the materials to match the difficulty level of university entrance tests and make necessary changes. Teachers do not rely on materials published by the government or national publishers for test preparation; instead, they prefer to compile materials from international publishers and the internet. The assessments inform students about their proficiency in the learning materials, not to enhance the teachers' teaching methods. The classrooms mainly focus on remedial or test drills in formative and summative assessments. These methods produce graduates who perform better than those from other schools in university entrance tests and excel in their chosen universities, both nationally and internationally.

Authors' Statement

Didi Sukyadi wrote sections 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6; Lukman Hakim contributed to the sections 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6; Joseph Foley worked on the section 2, 4, and 6; Dan Henry Gonzales contributed to the sections 2 and 6.

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References

- Alderson, J., & Wall, D. (1993). Does washback exist? *Applied Linguistics*, 14(2), 115-129. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/14.2.115>
- Bailey, K. M. (1996). Working for washback: A review of the washback concept in language testing. *Language Testing*, 13(3), 257-279. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026553229601300303>

- Barnes, M. (2017). Washback: Exploring what constitutes “good” teaching practices. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 30, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeap.2017.10.003>
- Booth, D. K. (2012). *Exploring the washback of the TOEIC in South Korea: A sociocultural perspective on student test activity* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. The University of Auckland.
- Booth, D. K. (2018). *The sociocultural activity of high stakes standardized language testing: TOEIC washback in a South Korean context*. Springer Cham.
- Brown, J. D. (1997). Testing washback in language education. *PASAA*, 27, 64-79.
- Buck, G. (1988). Testing listening comprehension in Japanese university entrance examinations. *JALT Journal*, 10, 15-42.
- Cheng, L. (2008). Washback, impact and consequences. In N. H. Hornberger (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of language and education* (pp. 2479-2494). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-30424-3_186
- Cheng, L., Sun, Y., & Ma, J. (2015). Review of washback research literature within Kane’s argument-based validation framework. *Language Teaching*, 48(4), 436-470.
- Cheng, L., Watanabe, Y., & Curtis, A. (2004). *Washback in language testing: Research contexts and methods*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications Inc.
- Dawadi, S. (2021). Factors affecting washback of a high-stakes English as a foreign language test. *Teaching English as a Second Language Electronic Journal (TESL-EJ)*, 25(3). <https://tesl-ej.org/pdf/ej99/a1.pdf>
- Esmonde, I. (2016). Power and privilege in learning sciences: Critical and sociocultural theories in learning. In I. Esmonde & A. N. Booker (Eds.), *Power and privilege in the learning sciences: Critical and sociocultural theories of learning* (1st ed., pp. 6-27). Routledge.

- Hamp-Lyons, L. (2000). Social, professional and individual responsibility in language testing. *System*, 28, 579-591. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0346-251X\(00\)00039-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0346-251X(00)00039-7)
- Hawkey, R. (2006). *Impact, theory, and practice* (Vol. 24). Cambridge University Press.
- Holm, L., & Kousholt, K. B. (2019). Beyond washback effect: A multidisciplinary approach exploring how testing becomes part of everyday school life focused on the construction of pupils' cleverness. *Annual Review of Critical Psychology*, 16, 917-952.
- Hughes, A. (1989). *Testing for language teachers*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hughes, A. (1993). *Washback and TOEFL 2000* [Unpublished manuscript]. University of Reading.
- Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. (2022). *Transformasi Seleksi Penerimaan Mahasiswa Baru pada PTN* [Transformation of new student admission selection at PTN]. *Kebijakan SNPMB* [SNPMB Policy], Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. <http://kebijakan-snpmb.bppp.kemdikbud.go.id>
- John-Steiner, V., & Mahn, H. (1996). Sociocultural approaches to learning and development: A Vygotskian framework. *Educational Psychologist*, 31(3-4), 191-206. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.1996.9653266>
- Khan, A. B. M. A., Aziz, M. S. A., & Stapa, S. H. (2019). Examining the factors mediating the intended washback of the English language school-based assessment: Pre-service ESL teachers' accounts. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences & Humanities*, 27(1), 51-68.
- Koné, K. (2024). An investigation into factors that shape Francophone African EFL learners' beliefs in learning English. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(3), 39-60.
- Mahmud, N., Lateh, M. H. M., Mahmud, N., Hassan, A. F., & Tarmizi, S. A. A. (2021). Washback impact of the MUET: The before and after effect of a high-stakes university English test in Malaysia. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(8), 1-17.

- Messick, S. (1996). Validity and washback in language testing. *Language Testing*, 13(3), 241-256. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026553229601300302>
- Munawaroh, N., Ijudin, Ainissyifa, H., & Fatonah, N. (2022). Revitalization of sociocultural values in pesantren. *Edukasi Islami: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 11(2), 683-694.
- Patten, M. L. (2000). *Understanding research methods: An overview of the essentials* (2nd ed.) Pyrczak Publishing.
- Patten, M. L. (2001). *Questionnaire research: A practical guide* (2nd ed.). Pyrczak Publishing.
- Razavipour, K., Mansoori, M., & Shooshtari, M. Z. (2020). Test takers' perspectives on an English language test in Iranian higher education: A washback study. *Issues in Educational Research*, 30(3), 1058-1083.
- Saefudin, A., Triharwanto, F., Farida, Y. E., & Mahalli. (2021). The sociocultural resilience of Islamic boarding school: Supporting and inhibiting factors. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, 633, 207-214. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220104.031>
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2021). Washback or backwash? Revisiting the status quo of washback and test impact in EFL contexts. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 8(3), 869-884.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2023). Native experts and reputable journals as points of reference: A study on research-article discussions. *Studies in English Language and Education*, 10(2), 562-574.
- Salmani Nodoushan, M. A. (2024). Language colonization or lingua franca? Demystifying the status quo of Persian. *International Journal of Language Studies*, 18(2), 63-90.
- Saukah, A. (2015). National exam in Indonesia and its washback effects. In F. A. Hamied, I. B. Yadnya, & I. G. Sosiowati (Eds.), *Developing indigenous models of English language teaching and assessment* (pp. 143-160). Udayana University Press.
- Stobart, G., & Eggen, T. J. H. M. (2012). High-stakes testing: Value, fairness and consequences. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 19(1), 1-6. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2012.639191>

- Sundayana, W., Meekaeo, P., Purnawarman, P., & Sukyadi, D. (2018). Washback of English national exams at ninth-grade level in Thailand and Indonesia. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 8(1), 167-176. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijal.v8i1.11478>
- Taib, F., Pakaya, U., & Abid. (2021). Students' voices on English language uses in an Islamic boarding school in Gorontalo. *Jambura Journal of English Teaching and Literature*, 2(2), 87-96. <https://doi.org/10.37905/jetl.v2i2.13084>
- Taylor, C. P. (2015). Sociocultural perspectives and characteristics. In R. Gunstone (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of science education* (pp. 981-983). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-6165-0_313-2
- Tsang, C. L., & Issacs, T. (2022). Hong Kong secondary students' perspectives on selecting test difficulty level and learner washback: Effects of a graded approach to assessment. *Language Testing*, 39(2), 212-238. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02655322211050600>
- Vernon, P. E. (1956). *The measurement of abilities*. University of London Press.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1962). *Thought and language*. MIT Press.
- Wall, D., & Alderson, J. C. (1993). Examining washback: The Sri Lankan impact study. *Language Testing*, 10(1), 41-69. <https://doi.org/10.1177/026553229301000103>
- Whitehead, G. E. K. (2014). *High-stakes testing washback: Korean high school English teachers' perspectives on the national English ability test* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Birmingham University.
- Yin, R. K. (2003). *Case study research: Design and methods* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.